

**SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION FROM “A” LANGUAGE INTO A “B”
LANGUAGE**

Alisher Khamidov

Senior Lecturer at UzSWLU

hamidovalisher5@gmail.com, +998909812625

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***Abstract.** This article deals with the issues of interpretation from Source language (SL) into Target language (TL) and selection of students for training interpreters.*

***Аннотация.** Данная статья посвящена проблеме устного перевода с родного языка на иностранный язык и отбору студентов для подготовки устных переводчиков*

***Аннотация.** Мазкур мақолада она тилидан чет тилига оғзаки таржима муаммолари ва талабаларни оғзаки таржимага ўргатиш учун танлаб олиш масалалари кўриб чиқилади*

There is hardly another question which triggers as heated a debate among interpreters worldwide as interpreting into the active foreign language, the so-called B language. Dejean le Feal (1998) goes as far as wondering if the trend towards interpretation into B is actually hurting the profession.

What is a “B” language?

This is the AIIC definition: "A language other than the interpreter's native language, of which she or he has a perfect command and into which she or he works from one of more of her or his other languages. Some interpreters work into a 'B' language in only one of the two modes of presentation."

This definition does not go into enough detail for training purposes. During the Hankuk University of Foreign Studies (HUFS) course, there were a number of discussions on this question. It was generally agreed that a 'B' is

- a language in which you can think - in a formal, structured (*eg* an interpreting) situation;
- a language in which you can deliver a clear and accurate message to conference participants, colleagues on relay and colleagues who share your 'A' language. So we have a little more to go on than 'perfect command'.

To take matters further we need to acknowledge the difference between a language of which someone has a 'perfect command' and his/her 'native language'. A 'B' language is one you have to handle with care because it is not your native language. (A language in which you are a guest, as a colleague once put it.) You have to acknowledge that there may well be problems with - among others - your:

- Prepositions
- Articles
- Tenses
- Collocations
- Idiom
- Vocabulary
- Pronunciation
- Accent

Since the aim is to deliver a clear, accurate message to listeners, interpreters working into their 'B' must be familiar with their areas of weakness and develop strategies for dealing with them. There was general agreement on the courses at Hankuk University of Foreign Studies that the best place to begin was to keep it simple. Awareness of working into a 'B' should not turn out to be a distraction. Interpreters should not use try out new expressions or rephrase ideas to the detriment of their message delivery. There is a need to focus on that, on ensuring that they convey what the speaker is saying quickly, using the correct vocabulary and register.

There are arguments for and against what is easier and more important: comprehension in the source language or expression in the target language. Ideally, of course, neither should be impaired. However, disregarding the issue of bilingualism in translation science, given the fact that the translator is a non-native speaker of one of the languages with which he works – either of the source language when he translates into his mother tongue, or of the target language when he translates into the non-mother tongue, the debate is a never-ending one, where certain conclusions can be drawn after a comprehensive assessment of the advantages and drawbacks of translation in both directions.

Interestingly enough, translation science has so far given rise to few research projects which address the differences between, and quality-related advantages and disadvantages of translation into the B language and into the A language on the basis of preliminarily set criteria. This article offers a summary of all aspects of the issue and attempts to provide the structured review of sporadic references in literature. Our investigations have focused on interpreting, the term "translation" is used as a collective noun with reference to both written or oral translation, i.e. interpreting.

Before making any statement related to the quality or the technique of interpretation, the reality of the interpreter's job should be examined. Where, in what situation and with what languages do interpreters work exclusively into their A language and their B language respectively; which are the factors determining directionality? While research offers very little in this respect, it can be generally said that interpreting into the A language, i.e. into the mother tongue is the dominant or in certain cases exclusive direction at major international organizations, such as the Joint Interpreting and Conference Service (widely known as SCIC by its French acronym) of the European Commission, and the Directorate for Interpretation of the European Parliament. Similarly, interpreting into the mother tongue dominates in the UN, the Council of Europe and NATO. These organizations work in close co-operations with AIIC, the International Association of Conference Interpreters headquartered in Geneva, which unequivocally considers translation into the A language to be superior. Interpreter teams working with "major languages" (English, French, German, Italian, Spanish, etc.) at international conferences staged in Western Europe are also composed on the basis of the mother tongue and attention is paid to eliminate interpreting from relay, which means that preferably each booth has interpreters who jointly cater for all of the official languages of the conference.

Western European free markets are not quite so rigid in requiring interpreting into the A language. Interpreters with German, English and French for their mother tongue report that in local or regional markets they are often required to work into their learned language, i.e. an interpreter with German mother tongue works into English or French and vice-versa. Graduate interpreter training in Germany has always laid a great emphasis on teaching interpreting into the B language. Working into the B language is deemed indispensable in this market as interpreters with the

appropriate mother tongue are not necessarily available at all times and clients therefore do not have a choice.

Working into the B language has always been part of the interpretation practice in Central and Eastern European countries, in some cases, it has become dominant. This applies to major international events, such as the so-called Central European summits where interpreting into the B language is done through relay as the interpreters are not members of an internationally organized team but are recruited by the local organizers, who, motivated also by financial reasons, tend to have recourse to opportunities offered by the local market. At a conference where the official languages are, say, Uzbek and Russian, it would probably be impossible anywhere in the world to provide an interpreter team which does not rely on relay and has two interpreters in each booth, who are capable of translating into their mother tongue directly from all of the other conference languages between them. Such meeting will inevitably require a relay language, which in general will be the language of the organizing country, or in cases where each delegation provides its own interpreters, the relay tends to be German or English – albeit these languages will not appear as official conference languages, nor are they likely to be the A language of any of the interpreters.

According to the findings of a survey conducted in Hungary in 2000 involving a hundred Hungarian conference interpreters, fifty percent of the respondents' work is done into their A language and fifty percent into their B language. Thirty-six percent of the respondents favour working into the B language. Several interpreters stated that the amount of work into the A language had increased since the political changeover: in the 1980's, the dominant direction of interpreting was into the B language.

In 2002, FIT and JTP, the Czech interpreters' association published a joint survey on the situation, qualification and working conditions of Central Eastern European interpreters (Katschinka 2002). The survey highlights the increasing role of international organizations in almost all of the countries of the region, resulting in a growing importance of interpretation into the A language. To the question of which was the dominant direction of interpreting, interpreters answered both directions were dominant in all of the countries, with the exception of Slovenia. Slovenian interpreters stated that seventy percent of their work is into their mother tongue.

In recent years, there has been a substantial modification in the interpreting practice of international organizations as well. With the increasing participation of Central and Eastern European countries, conference organizers were forced to involve interpreters who worked into their B language in a growing number of cases. According to an article on the quality of interpretation published in AIIC's web magazine *Communicate!* (Kahane 2000), interpreting from relay has become daily routine in the practice of SCIC and the European Parliament and is likely to be institutionalized after the enlargement in the near future. SCIC's strategy for 2004 specifically states that with 22 official and working languages it will be indispensable to employ all interpretation techniques, including relay and working into the B language (Memorandum 2002). The same applies to the European Parliament, whose Interpretation service lays a great emphasis on working with interpreters from the candidate countries, whose B languages, primarily English, French and German, is of a high standard of quality.

But how should students be selected for training interpreters?

According to our colleagues at Hankuk University of Foreign Studies (HUFS), there is a test so called a recall test, the applicant hears a 3-minute presentation and a topic of general interest

and renders it in another language. Before the task, the applicant is instructed to concentrate on listening and memorizing what she/he hears. No note-taking is allowed. The recall tasks are from B and/or C to A and from A to B, and the selection criteria include:

- Comprehension of the source language
- Production of the target language
- Understanding and reproduction of the “internal logic” of the message heard
- concentration and memory
- Presentation skills (voice, register, eye-contact...)
- Ability to cope with the situation.

In summary, interpretation into the B language is definitely in demand in the market, however, its significance is conspicuous primarily in the communication between minor languages and major languages on the one hand, and among minor languages on the other hand. Securing A language interpreters is often a financial question as in most local markets A language interpreters are few and far between and the costs of higher fees (in the case of interpreters coming from "more expensive" countries) very often exceed the Interpreting into the B language financial capabilities of organizers. Once less developed interpreting markets catch up with the standards of major international markets, if economic development so allows, if a uniform internal interpreting market emerges, interpreting into the B language may lose some of its significance. This, however, is unlikely to occur in the foreseeable future.

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